

FAIRification Plan Documentation

Document version control

Version	Date	Author	Author role	Modifications
0.1	29-01-2023	Cecilia Freire	Project Manager	Project information
0.2	01-04-2023	Paulo Meireles	FAIR Expert	Resources analysis and documentation, stakeholders, CQs and goal refinement.

Part I

1. Project Information

Project Initial Goals:

To collect and manage patient data related to rare diseases in a way that supports research and clinical efforts to improve the diagnosis, treatment, and overall care of individuals affected by rare diseases.

FAIR Project Stakeholders:

Type of Stakeholder	Role	Role Description
Domain Stakeholder	Patient Representative	Represents the interests and perspectives of patients with rare diseases and provides input on how patient data should be collected, managed, and used.
	Registry Manager	Responsible for supervising the collection, management, and analysis of patient data within a rare disease registry, and ensuring that the registry is used in accordance with ethical and legal standards.
	Clinician	A healthcare provider who diagnoses, treats, and manages patients with rare diseases, and who may use patient data to inform clinical care.
	Researcher	A scientist who studies rare diseases and seeks to advance understanding of their causes, treatments, and outcomes, and who may use patient data to inform research projects.
FAIR experts	Semantic Modeller	Responsible for developing ontologies and other semantic models to annotate and integrate patient data.
	FAIR Infrastructure Expert	An expert in developing and implementing FAIR infrastructure and data management practices.
	FAIRification Project Manager	Responsible for supervising the process of making data FAIR.
	FAIR Developer	A software developer with expertise in implementing FAIR principles, who is responsible for developing the technical infrastructure and tools needed to make resources FAIR.
	Data Custodian	Organisation responsible for the safe and secure storage, management, and sharing of patient data, and for ensuring that the data is used in

		accordance with ethical and legal standards.
--	--	--

Project Requirements:

Type of Requirement	Description
Data Security and Privacy	Data must be stored within the organization's premises to ensure compliance with data privacy regulations. Access to the data must be restricted to authorized users only. Patient data must be anonymized to protect patient privacy.
Interoperability	The database should be designed to be interoperable with other health data systems to facilitate data integration and exchange. The database should be compatible with common data exchange formats and standards, such as HL7 FHIR

2. FAIRification Targets

List of resources to be made FAIR:

Resource	Resource Description
patientReg	Legacy data collected from rare diseases patient since the hospital started using the Electronic Data Capture (EDC) system. Data stored in tabular format.
Unicorn EDC System v2.4	Current EDC system, open source and allow for extra functionality implementation.

List of available FAIR supporting infrastructure and limitations:

Infrastructure Item	Infrastructure Item Description	Item limitation
Data storage	Storage server that supports graph database, protected by the institution firewall. Supports SPARQL querying.	Does not allow exposing minimal metadata outside the organisation.
AAI	Authentication and authorisation system used to control access to the database API and endpoint.	-
Institution longevity plan	50 years for data and indefinite for metadata	-

Analysis Status: FAIRification **can proceed**. However, extra functionalities for supporting GUPRI would have to be developed by the FAIR developers.

Resources semantic status and limitations:

Resource Item	Resource Item Description	Item limitation
Legacy data	Legacy data include headers already annotated with ontologies and some that need to be clarified by the data steward. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ontologised headers: symptom (Phenotype and 	Unclear headers need clarification with data steward.

	<p>Disease Ontology - PATO), genetic information (Human Phenotype Ontology - HPO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear headers: id, name, name2, country, etn., age, results 	
Unicorn EDC System	Collects the same data items and in the same format as the legacy data, hence needing the same type of clarification.	Unclear headers need clarification with data steward.

Status: FAIRification can proceed after the clarification of unclear headers.

Part II

3. FAIRification Domain

FAIRification type: given the different nature of the two resources, we would use both types of FAIRification: *retrospective* for already existing data, and *de novo* for the data to be collected.

Semantic Types Identified from Current Data:

Semantic Type	Description	Description Source
Patient	A person who receives medical attention, care, or treatment, or who is registered with medical professional or institution with the purpose to receive medical care when necessary.	NCIT_C16960
Rare Disease	A disease or disorder that affects fewer than 1 in 2,000 people in Europe.	(European Commission, 2020)
Diagnosis	The investigation, analysis and recognition of the presence and nature of disease, condition, or injury from expressed signs and symptoms	NCIT_C15220
Treatment	An action or administration of therapeutic agents to produce an effect that is intended to alter the course of a pathologic process.	NCIT_C15368
Genetic Information	A data item that is about genetic material including polymorphisms, disease alleles, and haplotypes.	OBI_0001404

Domain Scope (abstract style chosen):

We hereby describe the domain scope of usual information utilised by clinicians and researchers when treating and investigating patients with a rare disease. The data from **rare disease** patients usually includes **patient** details such as name, age, gender, ethnicity, and contact information. That is used for generating statistics and contacting patients in case of clinical trials, for instance. If published, patient details must be pseudonymised and anonymised.

The patient's medical history is essential for understanding the progression of the rare disease and assessing the effectiveness of treatments. This includes information on previous **diagnoses**, hospitalizations, and medical procedures. Detailed information on the **symptoms** experienced by patients is important for treatment and for sharing knowledge between centres. This includes the symptom's frequency, duration and severity.

Since most rare diseases are genetic in origin, information on the patient's genetic makeup is collected, including any **genetic mutations** or **variations**. This data is essential for understanding the underlying causes of the rare disease and developing targeted **treatments**. *Status:* the description above is **validated** by experts.

4. Reuse stakeholders

Stakeholder role	Stakeholder role main goal
Patient representatives	reuse the data to increase awareness and understanding of rare diseases
Clinicians	reuse the data to diagnose and treat patients with rare diseases
Researchers	reuse the data to find new treatment options for rare disease patients
Healthcare providers	reuse the data to improve patient management

Status: list **validated** by domain and FAIR experts.

Part III

5. Goals Refinement

Refinement type chosen: bottom-up approach

Competency Questions:

ID	Question	Related Stakeholder(s)
CQ1	What is the age range and gender distribution of patients with a particular rare disease?	Patient representative
CQ2	How do the symptoms of a particular rare disease vary among different patient groups (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity)?	Patient representative
CQ3	What are the most common symptoms associated with a particular rare disease?	Clinician
CQ4	What previous diagnoses and treatments have been tried for patients with a particular rare disease?	Clinician
CQ5	What specific genetic mutations or variations are associated with a particular rare disease?	Clinician
CQ6	Are there any subgroups of patients with a specific rare disease who share similar clinical or genetic characteristics?	Clinician
CQ7	What are the most effective treatments or interventions for patients with a specific rare disease, and what are the potential risks or side effects associated with these treatments?	Health care provider

Refined goals (considering stakeholders and competency questions): Figure 1.

Refinement:

CQ(s) ID	Goal
CQ1	"Patient awareness of RD is improved", "Patient management is improved"
CQ2, CQ3, CQ4, CQ5	"Cohorts for clinical trials are identified", "Novel drug candidates are identified", "Disease progression is predicted"
CQ6	"Patient management is improved"
CQ7	"RDs inequalities are reduced"

6. FAIRification Solutions

Similar FAIRification projects with candidate solutions:

FAIRification Project	FAIRification Project Description	Candidate Solutions
European Joint Program on Rare Diseases (EJP RD)	EJP RD aims to promote the use of FAIR data principles in rare disease research by developing guidelines and tools for data management and sharing. This includes the development of a common data model and data dictionary to facilitate data harmonization and integration across different databases and research projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EJP RD CDE Semantic Model to define common data elements • EJP RD Metadata Model to describe the patient registry • FAIR Data Point to expose the registry metadata (F)
VASCERN Registry	The VASCERN registry is a patient registry that aims to collect and share clinical data on rare vascular diseases across Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs) to be implemented on the Unicorn EDC. • Data conversion tool to convert data generated by Unicorn EDC to Linked Data.

Goals aligned to FAIR principles: Figure 2.

Possible solutions for identified principles:

Goal ID	Principle	Possible Solution
T7,	F1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use PURL or W3ID to provide references to dataset, metadata and data
T1, T4, T7	F2	Provide metadata to describe resource given the stakeholder's goals: possible reuse candidate is the EJP RD Metadata Model
	F3	Use of W3ID provide a path that concatenates metadata and data identifier
	F4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata to be indexed by the EJP RD Virtual Platform • Metadata to be indexed by Bing
T2, T5, T8	A1.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse protocols provided by the Fair Data Point (FDP) • Use SPARQL endpoint by Garlic
	A1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use AAI system from organisation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement AAI system by a third party • Include all information on metadata (T10)
T3, T6, T9	I1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata defined in SQL • Metadata defined in RDF • Metadata defined in OWL
	I2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse of vocabularies reused by EJP RD CDE Semantic Model • Reuse of vocabularies reused by EJP RD Metadata Model (T12) • Reuse of DCAT, DCT, SKOS
	I3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • References by EJP RD Model • References by EJP RD CDE Semantic Model
	R1.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include CC licence for metadata • Include own licence for data
	R1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provenance information provided to fulfill stakeholders goals, reuse model
	R1.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse standards reused in EJP • Reuse standards reused in Vascern (T13) • Use Bioschemas
G1, G2	F1, A2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use longevity plan from institution • Hire third party storage • Use public repository (e.g., GitHub)

7. FAIRification Decisions

Chosen solutions:

Principle	Chosen Solution	Choice reasoning
F1 – Unique ID	Use W3ID	Provides global, unique, persistent identifier
F2 – Rich Metadata	Define own metadata model reusing the EJP RD Metadata Model, additional terms accordingly to goal model	The EJP RD Metadata Model already reuses other community standards, is compliant with the Virtual Platform Requirements and, by doing so, we increase interoperability

F3 – Linking (meta)data	Include a field on metadata referring to page with information on how to get access to data	Including direct URL to data is not ideal when we want to avoid unauthorised access to it
F4 – Metadata is searchable	Metadata to be indexed by EJP RD VP	EJP RD VP already indexes other RD datasets, which increases our visibility within the RD research community
A1.1 – Open communication protocol	Use functionalities provided by the FDP	FDP provides but HTTP and SPARQL communication protocols
A1.2 – Authentication and authorisation	Use organisation's system	Reduce cost and increase trust within the organisation
A2 – Metadata longevity	Use organisation's plan	Reduce cost and increase trust within the organisation
I1 – Knowledge representation	Data to be stored in RDF	Community standard that allows for data to be easily connected with other datasets
I2 – FAIR Vocabularies	EJP RD Metadata model and EJP RD CDE Semantic Model vocabularies	The referenced models reuse other vocabularies that are FAIR in different levels
I3 – Qualified references	EJP RD Metadata model and EJP RD CDE Semantic Model vocabularies	The referenced models reuse other vocabularies that are FAIR in different levels
R1.1 – Licence	Define licence for metadata using CC, reuse organisation's standard licence for data	Metadata can be made public, so CC is a good fit. Reusing organisation's standard licence for data builds trust within it and avoid other legal concerns
R1.2 - Provenance	Provenance provided according to goal models	Additional data is needed to fulfil our stakeholders goals
R1.3 – Community standards	Reuse of standards provided by the EJP RD Metadata model and EJP RD CDE Semantic Model vocabularies	Increased interoperability with other RD resources

Figures

Figure 1 - Goals per stakeholder

Figure 2 - Complete goal diagram with alignment to FAIR principles

References

European Comission. (2020). *Rare Diseases*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/health/non_communicable_diseases/rare_diseases_en